

1. What are stromatolites, and approximately how old are they? (2)
2. Why are microfossils hard to study? (1)
3. Describe the Miller experiments. Why were they so controversial? (2)
4. Why are phospholipids key molecules for the apparition of cellular life? (1)
5. What does panspermia claim? (1)
6. What are the advantages and disadvantages to panspermia? (1)
7. Which of the following statements is correct? (1)
 - Planet Earth and the sun were formed 4.5 billion years ago
 - Planet Earth and the sun were formed 4.5 million years ago
 - Planet Earth and the sun were formed 450 billion years ago
 - Planet Earth and the sun were formed 45 billion years ago
8. Which ONE of the following statements is correct? Stromatolites (1)
 - Are sediments containing fossils of the first reptiles appearing on Earth
 - Were formed during the stellar explosion which gave rise to Earth
 - Contain microfossils resembling contemporary bacteria
 - Appeared 3.5 billion years ago, but have now disappeared
9. In his “prebiotic soup experiment”, Stanley Miller used a reducing atmosphere, water, heat, inorganic compounds and lightning to produce which ONE of the following: (1)
 - Oxygen
 - Simple unicellular organisms
 - Lipids
 - Amino acids
10. Which ONE of these statements is incorrect? The Miller experiments... (1)
 - can lead to the production of nucleobases
 - requires high H_2 atmospheric concentrations, which may have not been present on Earth
 - requires a huge amount of energy that could have been provided by lightening
 - does not make sense, as Chandra Wickramasinghe and Fred Hoyle demonstrated life came from space
11. Why are RNA molecules likely to have appeared before proteins and DNA? (1)
 - Because RNA is more stable than DNA
 - Because RNA molecules are found in less evolved organisms, like bacteria
 - Because the Miller experiment showed RNA molecules can be created in prebiotic conditions
 - Because RNA molecules can display catalytic activities
12. Which ONE of the following cannot be carried out by ribozymes? (1)
 - RNA cleavage
 - RNA ligation
 - Formation of peptide bonds
 - Reverse transcription (to produce DNA)

Points earned: _____ out of a possible 14 points

13. Which ONE of these properties describes phospholipids best? (1)
- They are hydrophilic molecules
 - They are hydrophobic molecules
 - They are neither hydrophobic or hydrophilic
 - They are both hydrophobic and hydrophilic (amphipathic)
14. Which scientists proposed the concept of panspermia? (1)
- Fred Hoyle
 - Chandra Wickramasinghe
 - Paul Nurse
 - Fred Sirieix
 - Thomas Cech
15. Which molecule is key to the apparition of compartmentalisation? (1)
- RNA
 - Fatty Acids
 - Phospholipids
 - Amino acids
16. What is the major issue associated with panspermia? (1)
- Life cannot come from space
 - Very little experimental evidence underpins the theory
 - Only viruses have been isolated from asteroids
 - Only bacteria have ever been isolated from asteroids

Points earned: _____ out of a possible 4 points

Question	Points	Score
1	2	
2	1	
3	2	
4	1	
5	1	
6	1	
7	1	
8	1	
9	1	
10	1	
11	1	
12	1	
13	1	
14	1	
15	1	
16	1	
Total:	18	

Points earned: _____ out of a possible 0 points